

AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF EMPLOYEES' INVOLVEMENT IN 5S QUALITY PRACTICES OF MALAYSIA ARMED FORCES

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ABSTRACT

Organizations are adapting to new and demanding changes in the digital economy. One of the ways to respond to the challenges is through quality improvement. In a military context, organizations such as the Military Armed Forces of Malaysia (MAF) has deployed, among others, the 5S quality management tool. Many believe that the success of quality management depends largely on the "people" of the organization. This study explores employees' perception of 5S practices within MAF and seeks to find answers to the main question, "How would MAF improve employees' involvement in 5S practices?". Data was collected from MAF personnel through interviews to meet the research objectives. Results from the qualitative study reveal five perceived important elements that would drive employees' active participation in 5S. We discuss the implications for military managers and future directions of research.

Keywords: 5S, quality management, military, quality practices, employee involvement

INTRODUCTION

Globalization mainly contributed to the advancement of information technology and profoundly impacted organizations as both public and private sectors are compelled to heighten their competitiveness. This pressure has led organizations to rethink ways to remain sustainable, and one of the crucial strategies is to gain an edge in providing quality services. Consequently, the deployment of sound quality management practices, such as "5S", is mandatory to ensure the entire organization operates efficiently in processes, costs, and standards that entail higher quality products and services. On the other hand, organizations that do not adopt such systems will incur higher operating costs due to errors and delays leading to declining performance. The successful implementation of 5S practices has attracted considerable attention over many years. Primarily, in any organization, the "people factor", which often refers to managers and employees, is central to the successful implementation of any quality management systems. In a military organization, in which mission-critical tasks require high precision and standards, the need for a good understanding of employees' perception of the imperatives of quality systems in organizational performance is crucial. In recent years, researchers and practitioners have been paying increasing attention to the phenomenon of quality management and its impact on organizational performance. Although many studies have addressed the issues pertaining to 5S implementation,

very few have examined the 5S practices in military organization in Malaysia, particularly the Malaysia Armed Forces (MAF). Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the level of awareness among military personnel and perceived efforts that would encourage employees' participation to ensure its successful implementation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

5S DEFINITION AND CONCEPTS

According to Adzrie & Vincent (2020), the original philosophy of the Japanese words "Seiri", "Seiton", "Seiso", "Shitsuke", and "Seiketsu" is classification, order, cleanliness, standardization, and consistency. Additionally, other researchers defined 5S as one of the quality tools used to reduce waste and optimize productivity by maintaining an orderly workplace and using visual cues to achieve more consistent operational results (Janakiraman & Gopal, 2007; Gapp et al., 2008). In line with this view, some other researchers defined the 5S principle as a quality practice that focuses on a workplace organization and continuous improvement system that lays the foundation for all other lean improvement activities (Bain, 2010; Hirata, 2001). In this study, we define 5S as the principles of work that allow users to create a structured plan to maintain classification, order, and cleanliness regularly, leading to profitability, health, environment operation, personnel morale, reliability, and performance, which in turn would increase the competitiveness of the organization.

THE "PEOPLE FACTOR" IN 5S IMPLEMENTATION

Primarily, effective organizations have employees who are committed and make contributions to organizational success (Cichosz et al., 2020). In other words, organizations that thrive in an intensely competitive environment predominantly emphasize their people, namely leaders, managers and employees, as the most valuable resource (Oladipo, 2011; Cherif, 2020). It is believed that a good relationship between employees and managers would create a better working environment and a more productive workforce (Edwards et al., 2008; Uddin et al., 2019). Indeed, when employees perceive proper organizational support, they reciprocate with positive returns such as higher commitment leading to the successful implementation of tasks and projects (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). As tasks become more complex in the changing environments, managers need to play an active role in guiding the employees, anticipating problems and providing clear direction to help increase the overall organization's performance (Liao, 2017; Turesky et al., 2020). Today, with the emergence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, where powerful Internet computing and intelligent systems permeate the workplace, organizations, such as MAF, must understand the dynamism of the "people factor" in relation to 5S. In the past, studies have examined 5S from various perspectives, including manufacturing, healthcare, education sectors, etc. Nevertheless, studies on implementing 5S practice as part of the quality management tool in a military setting have been limited. Hence this research seeks to understand employees' awareness of their roles and how 5S can be successfully implemented through employees' active involvement at MAF is worthwhile.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this study, a qualitative method was employed in this research as it seeks to obtain in-depth answers to the “why” question rather than “what” (Yin, 2014). Since the study seeks to address the employees' perceptions of 5S successful implementation in a military organization, the unit of analysis is military personnel of selected federal and state offices from three types of services: Army, Navy and Air Force which are located in Malaysia Armed Forces Headquarters. A group of six employees representing every service within MAF were chosen to be the respondents in this study.

THE INTERVIEWS

The inclusion criterion for the respondents is set as employees who have experience in the implementation of 5S practices at their workplace. Interviews were conducted using verbal interview questions. Ericson and Simon (1984) and Kuusela and Paul (2000) defined the exploratory research method emphasizes the interviewee's verbal process of previous experiences. A semi-structured interview is used for this study because this technique will enable the researcher freedom to exercise his or her own initiative in following up on an interviewee's answer to the question (Rusli & Hasbee, 2011).

The total number of respondents selected for the interviews was six MAF employees who were actively involved in the 5S program. At the beginning part of the interview session, the participants were provided with an explanation of the research aims and the tasks they needed to perform. The duration of each discussion was about an hour. Broad and open-ended questions such as “What do you understand about 5S?” and “Why does MAF introduce and implement 5S practices?” were posed. The researcher summarized the discussion during the sessions. All sessions were audio-recorded and later transcribed.

ANALYSIS

Before content analysis can begin, it needs to be preserved in a form that can be analyzed. Consequently, the researchers transcribed the recorded interviews data into an interview transcript before the content analysis could begin. Following the procedure proposed by Krippendorff (2013), the recorded data then was categorized into themes and inter-relationships.

Finally, the next step in the qualitative content analysis technique is concluding the coded data, as Rusli and Hasbee (2011) suggested. Drawing conclusions involves the process of making inferences and presenting the constructions of meanings derived from the data. The easiest way to present the meaning of the data is by using the concept map. A concept map is used to interpret the data and ensure a better understanding of the findings. According to Kinchin et al. (2008), concept maps are useful in representing information gathered during interviews, stimulating deeper responses, and correcting any areas of misunderstanding.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings from the interviews.

EMPLOYEE AWARENESS OF 5S PRACTICES

From the responses, employees gained awareness and knowledge of 5S practices in MAF through means of training, department initiatives through promotional communication, and being practically involved in 5S tasks.

"Since I am practically involved in this thing, I become more aware of what actually 5S is and what those benefits gain from this practice" - Respondent 2

"I attended training on 5S organized for our department some time ago, and that was how I came to know about it" - Respondent 1

As stated by the respondents, factors such as training and department initiatives were consistent with previous quality management-related theories. As stated in Deming's 14 Management's Principles (1982) and Crosby's 14 Points of Quality Improvement (1979), it is very much important for the organization to take proactive initiatives to organize or send their members for quality training so that they will be continuously aware and trained in the principles of 5S. Besides that, Juran (n.d.), in his Juran's Quality by Design (1992), also stressed that it was important for quality members to have continuous training for better understanding and awareness. Additionally, one factor that is 'practically involved' has been cited as one of the ways to increase awareness among employees so that they will have a better understanding of the importance of 5S. Figure 1 depicts the concept map of employee awareness.

Figure 1: Concept Map of Employee Awareness

EMPLOYEES' INVOLVEMENT

Top Management Support

One of the most mentioned factors contributing to employees' involvement in 5S is top management support. This can be found in the responses given by all respondents, Respondents 1-6. Examples of respondents' statements are given below:

"Another recipe to motivate the continuous involvement of the staff is the top management support towards this program. Thanks to all the zone leaders, the facilitators, and the top management because they are really committed and supportive in encouraging our staff to exercise these quality practices". - Respondent 3

"The zone leaders encourage sharing of 5S experiences among our departments...this reinforces the importance of the practice, and we can learn about best practices" - Respondent 4

The finding is consistent with previous studies that suggested that in order to have a dedicated and committed employee towards the implementation of 5S programs, the top management needs to be proactive (Agostini et al., 2019) in introducing and promoting the importance of exercising quality practices throughout the organization (Bhat et al., 2019; Balzer, 2015). In essence, top management leadership and effective communication would help to accomplish the objectives of the 5S project and ensure its sustainability. Additionally, knowledge-sharing efforts promoted by top management are valuable in motivating employees' involvement (Bartezzaghi et al., 2017, Shamim et al., 2016, Schuh et al., 2014 and Liu et al., 2006). Hence, we propose the following hypothesis:

RP1: Top management support has a significant relationship with employees' involvement in 5S practices

DEPARTMENT INITIATIVES

The 'department's initiatives' factor is also one of the factors that help in promoting active employees' participation in 5S, as shown in the following responses:

"Constant communication to us about 5S practices will be useful, for example, email from the Head of Department or, a campaign in the newsletter ...can serve as a reminder for us" - Respondent 1

"Apart from creating awareness, it is also useful to set an intervention plan ...in case the practices do not achieve the outcomes perhaps additional support programme or measures can be put in place" - Respondent 5

The findings align with the Sociotechnical Systems theory, which posits the importance of the interdependency of social and technical aspects of an organization. Primarily, past research suggested it is imperative that managers can connect social processes and decision processes

(Erol et al., 2016; Adolph et al., 2014). Similarly, Lawler et al. (1995) stated that it is important for organizations to have intervention plans that encourage higher participation from employees, thus enabling them to carry out their responsibilities well. Indeed, military personnel's understanding of 5S quality practices is a precursor to the successful implementation of such initiatives. Therefore, the second research proposition is:

RP2: Department initiatives have a significant relationship with employees' involvement in 5S practices

RECOGNITION

Besides that, 'recognition' was one of the critical factors that drove their sense of involvement in the 5S initiatives, as shown in the statement below:

"Normally, the members in this zone, I mean the winning zone, will be given a certificate from the Director. As a result of their good achievement in exercising the 5S practices. This certification can be classified as a reward for the staff for their active involvement and contribution in the 5S program". - Respondent 5

In line with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory (1943), to fulfil their esteem needs, employees are motivated by rewards as a recognition (Frankl, 2000; Wong, 2016) of his/her active participation in 5S practices. Further, Baht (2019) claims that individuals are motivated by recognition, which will lead to greater involvement (Yang, 2012; Paré & Tremblay, 2007). S. Thomas Foster (2017) listed that recognition is one factor contributing to the active participation amongst employees in the quality movement activity in Crosby' 14 steps. We offer the third research proposition:

RP3: Recognition has a significant relationship with employees' involvement in 5S practices.

PASSION

On top of that, 'passion' has been cited as one of the contributing factors to employees' involvement in 5S. For example, Respondent 3 asserted that,

"I think we will do anything for the Department not just because our duty requires it but for the good of the Force" - Respondent 3

This finding parallels the studies by Meyer and Allen (1991), Veličković et al. (2014) and Uddin et al. (2019), which assert that when the employee is passionately involved with the organization, one will exert his full energy to be committed to achieving organizational goals. In this study, employees are driven to achieve the desired outcomes of MAF obtaining 5S quality certification from the National Productivity Council, which will signify MAF's commitment to high-quality practices. Hence, the fourth proposition is as follows:

RP4: Employees' passion has a significant relationship with employees' involvement in 5S practices.

FACILITATOR'S COMMITMENT

Next, 'facilitator's commitment' has been reported as one of the contributors to the 5S successful implementation in this study. Previous studies conducted by Hasaan et al. (2013) and Wakhlu (2009) affirmed that heads of departments or committees are people managers, task managers, facilitators, inspirers, and information processes that facilitate the quality movement. Ketvirtis (2011) and Farkas (2003) pointed out that facilitators are responsible for assessing the progress of the 5S project as this is vital to ensure project continuance and success at the operational level. The following statement supports this:

"Several elements actually support the successful implementation of 5S; one of them is the facilitator's role that is the most important because the top management will have the mechanism to drive all those activities related to 5S and cooperation from facilitators, whether they are committed or not is key" - Respondent 6

RP5: The facilitator's commitment has a significant relationship with employees' involvement in 5S practices

Figure 2 summarises the findings for elements perceived as promoting employees' involvement in 5S practices at MAF.

Figure 2: Concept Map of Employees' Involvement in 5s Practices

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

It is believed that the successful implementation of 5S practices can contribute to better productivity and organizational performance. From the results, we propose several factors influencing employees' involvement in 5S practices: top management support, department initiatives, employee recognition, passion, and facilitator's commitment. In essence, quality management initiatives have to be spearheaded by the leaders at the top ranks of the MAF hierarchy. More importantly, to sustain quality improvement, organizational learning seems imperative to allow for valuable experience gained along the process to be developed into best practices. This study revealed that MAF had taken initiatives to create awareness about 5S tools among its employees through training and departmental communication channels. Managers are encouraged to promote the 5S project by employing institutional campaigns and using multiple communications channels. As in any quality management programme, it is worthwhile to continuously educate the leaders to increase the adoption rate within MAF. Proactive leadership and commitment at various levels are essential in successfully implementing the 5S practices. For instance, effective communication and sound execution plans at the departmental level are crucial as these would reinforce the importance of quality practices regularly. Likewise, 5S facilitators who are closer to the operational level should constantly review and assess its implementation and provide feedback for further enhancement of the programme. At the organizational level, MAF managers are advised to consider rewarding employees who have shown a high commitment to carrying out their work according to the 5S practices. This would motivate higher employees participation in achieving a common organizational goal.

This research is concerned with employees' perception of 5S practices and how their involvement in the project could be improved. Further studies involving a larger sample size could be carried out to ascertain our research propositions quantitatively. As quality management discipline grows in importance, particularly in the era of digitalization, a similar study in different industry settings, for example, healthcare, logistics, education, hospitality and other areas, is worthwhile and recommended.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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